

European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research infrastructure
PLUS

Site and platform operators training module report

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Abbreviation

SPF	Site and Platform Forum
RI	Research Infrastructure
PI	Principal investigator
WG	Working group
SPCs	Site and Platform Coordinators
SO	Standard Observation
WP	Work Package
eLTER	European integrated long-term ecosystem, critical and socio-ecology research
LTSER	Long-term socio-ecological research (platform)
EO	Earth observation
DEIMS-SDR	Dynamic ecological information management system- site and dataset register
ReLTER	eLTER R package

Summary

eLTER Sites and LTSER Platforms, distributed across Europe, make up the backbone of the foreseen eLTER Research Infrastructure (RI). The Site and Platform Coordinators (SPCs) are persons with different roles (Primary investigators (PIs), site managers, site coordinators, LTSER Platform managers, etc.) taking responsibility for Site or Platform operations. To support the SPCs, a Site and Platform Forum (SPF) was established by eLTER PLUS WP2 in 2020 as a forum for interaction and collaboration. The SPF organises frequent virtual webinars and has also organised several physical training events. With these webinars and events, the SPCs are informed about relevant technology developments and emerging tools, eLTER Standard Observation variables, new methods and workflows, site management, visualisation, data analysis, stakeholder engagement, transversal skills, and implementing the whole system approach at their Sites and Platforms. In spring 2024, approximately 550 people are listed in the SPF list and the participation in webinars has frequently exceeded 100 attendees.

SPF is also organised in working groups (WGs), aiming at collecting and summarising the opinions of SPCs and taking care that relevant aspects for SPCs are considered in the SPF and in the current and future development of eLTER RI. Among the WGs, Training was early on recognised as one of the most important issues for the SPCs. The Training working group was established during the first Sites and Platforms Forum (SPF) meeting (13 Jan 2021). Training needs were collected through two online questionnaires, performed during and soon after the pandemic period.

Data management and handling was considered one of the most relevant topics in the SPC training and one in-person workshop was organised (Lyon, France, 7-9 February 2023). The first in-person meeting of the SPF was also organised (Lunz, Austria, 2-5 October 2023).

The Training working group of SPF has met virtually several times, discussing the potential training needs of SPCs, and brainstorming the ideas of what kind of training could be provided and who could be the potential trainers. So far, the working group provided 12 training webinars, with wide attendance. Webinars were recorded, to make the information available to those who could not participate. The recordings were further edited to produce training videos which are available through eLTER Youtube channel. In addition, a training section was added to the eLTER website (<https://elter->

ri.eu/elter-training). The training has been categorised under specific topics to facilitate findability of the materials. In general, the feedback on organised training events has been positive.

At the time of the Deliverable completion, investigated interest for topics for future trainings included: “Data sharing through the eLTER services”; “Publishing datasets and data papers”; “Data sharing including harmonisation and storage”; “Interaction with stakeholders”; “Funding opportunities”

1 Sites and Platforms Forum

The eLTER Sites and LTSER Platforms, distributed across Europe, make up the backbone of the foreseen eLTER Research Infrastructure (RI). The Site and Platform Coordinators (SPCs) consist of a diverse group of job titles: Primary investigators (PIs), site managers, site coordinators, LTSER Platform managers, etc. A common denominator for all SPCs is that they are persons taking responsibility for eLTER Site or an eLTSER Platform operations and having the best overview of a wide variety of activities that take place at the facility.

To support the SPCs, a Site and Platform Forum (SPF) was established by eLTER PLUS WP2 in 2020 as a forum for interaction and collaboration. The SPF organises frequent virtual webinars and has also organised several physical training events. With these webinars and events, the SPCs are informed about relevant technology developments and emerging tools to ensure continued technical state of the art at Sites and Platforms; training on e.g. eLTER Standard Observation variables, new methods and workflows, site management, visualisation, data analysis, stakeholder engagement, transversal skills, and implementing the whole system approach at their Sites and Platforms.

Coordination of the SPF has been done from the eLTER PLUS project, but in an increasing manner, the SPCs themselves are involved in brainstorming, innovating and implementing the interactions. One of the primary activities conducted with the SPF was inviting them to participate in specific working groups aimed at gathering ideas and summarizing them for consideration in the development of the eLTER RI. Three groups were established: (1) Training Working Group, (2) Data Management & Information Cluster, and (3) Funding. In spring 2024, approximately 550 people are listed in the SPF list and the participation in webinars has frequently exceeded 100 attendees (See Table 1 below).

2 Site and Platform Coordinators Training needs

2.1 Training working group

SPF Working groups are concrete pathways between SPCs and eLTER projects. The working groups aim at collecting and summarising the opinions of SPCs and take care that aspects that are relevant for SPCs are dealt with in the SPF and are considered in the development of eLTER RI.

Training was early on recognised as one of the most important issues for the Site and Platform Coordinators (SPCs), and thus a Training working group was established during the first Sites and Platforms Forum (SPF) meeting (13 Jan 2021). The main goal of this WG was to identify the most urgent and essential training topics from the SPF and to offer appropriate training sessions accordingly.

Ulrike Obertegger (FEM-CRI, Italy) and Ana Marta Gonçalves (University of Aveiro, Portugal) have acted as training working group conveners. The working group has met virtually and has been discussing the potential training needs of SPCs, and brainstorming the ideas of what kind of training could be provided and who could be the potential trainers. Also, the working group provided a number of training webinars, with a significant attendance (see 3.2 below).

Wider input for SPC's needs and interest regarding the trainings were also collected. This was done during the sessions in the following SPF meetings run by the working group and through online questionnaires sent to all SPCs (see chapter 2.2).

2.2 Questionnaires

As the SPF is a new body in eLTER, it is important to start with a survey of the needs of SPCs for the Forum. We have done two questionnaires to have a wider perspective of what topics for different training SPCs would like to have, and what format they see most useful and interesting (2nd questionnaire). Detailed results are presented in Annex 7.1 and 7.2.

The first questionnaire (Annex 7.1) was open from 16th June 2021 until 27th August 2021, and we received altogether 89 responses. The second one (Annex 7.2) was submitted two years later, from 31st August to 2nd October 2023, and there were 90 responses.

The questionnaire started by asking the ecosystem type in which the respondents were working and then proposed a “tickable” list of topics organised in categories.

The first questionnaire included the following categories (top voted topics):

- Data management (top voted topics: Publishing datasets and data papers; Data sharing through the eLTER services; Data sharing including harmonisation and storage)
- Access (top topic: Support to site platform coordinators on providing access to sites)
- Data analyses (top voted topics: Time-series analysis; Spatial analysis; Remote sensing and earth observation (EO) data)
- New technologies (top topic: sensors)
- Monitoring procedures (top voted topics: eLTER Standard Observations - abiotic site characteristics; eLTER Standard Observations - biotic heterogeneity; eLTER Standard Observations - water budget).

The second questionnaire included the following categories (top voted topics):

- Data management (top voted topics: Data sharing through the eLTER services (e.g., data sharing including harmonisation and storage & preparing metadata; FAIR principle); Publishing datasets and data papers (e.g., GBIF, biodiversity data); Using DEIMS-SDR for describing sites and datasets)
- Access (top topic: Support to site platform coordinators on providing access to sites)
- Science communication (top voted topics: Interaction with stakeholders; Citizen science)
- Data usage & analysis (top voted topics: Time-series analysis; DataLabs as the environment to do analyses (i.e. working collaboratively on analytics); Data access/visualising data (Data Integration Platform)
- New technologies (top topic: sensors)
- Site Management (top voted topics: Funding opportunities; Site labelling process (tools to evaluate the "status" of a site in terms of category)

In the 2nd questionnaire, as the pandemic period was over, we asked also on the preferred format and duration of the training events. Approximately 50% of responses preferred the on-line format, with duration of 3-4 hours. However, also in presence and hybrid format and longer duration (up to 2-3 days) were mentioned.

The questionnaire results were presented in general SPF meetings and have been used to plan the content of SPF webinars. Also, results on the “training needs” emerging from the webinars were presented at the annual meetings of eLTER PLUS.

3 Organised trainings

3.1 On site event: eLTER tools

3.1.1 Workshop content

Data management and handling was considered one of the most relevant topics in the SPC training needs questionnaire. At the same time new tools were developed in the context of other WPs of eLTER PLUS, and in order to make them known and support their usage, a physical workshop on the eLTER tools was organised.

The workshop took place on 7-9 February 2023 in Lyon, France, and INRAE (linked third party of CNRS) took care of local logistics. The general programme is presented below, and the details in Annex 7.3.

Tue 7 February 2023

- 9:30-13 DataLabs (UK CEH)
- 14-17 DEIMS-SDR (EAA)

Wed 8 February 2023

- 9-13 Cookie cutting (UK CEH)
- 14-17 Site visit, Yzeron catchment (in DEIMS-SDR and [here](#))

Thu 9 February 2023

- 9-13 ReLTER (BGU; CNR)
- 14-16:30 Pheno-App (CSIC)

3.1.2 Application process and participants

For the application process we used an online registration form. In addition of the basic information, including if they work on eLTER Site or eLTER Platform, we asked potential participants about their experience on using R, QGIS, Python and involvement in papers using special analysis or software repositories (i.e. GitLab, GitHub). We also asked potential participants to write a few sentences about the following topics:

- 1) Yourself
- 2) Your experience in spatial software
- 3) people/community in your site/country you will be able to transfer the knowledge you gained in the workshop
- 4) Your expectations from this workshop
- 5) Your experience in the use of the public repository of data (i.e. Zenodo)?

Altogether we received 29 applications, and we could accommodate (space limitation) 24 participants. Due to last minute cancellation, 22 participants were present in Lyon. The gender balance was almost met (10 female, 12 male). Most participants were scientists (11), but also data managers (5), Site and Platform coordinators (3) and PhD students (3). Although most of the participants worked in eLTER projects, it was positive that 9 were not, which shows that the information of the workshop had been distributed also beyond the project. Most of the participants (18) also worked at an eLTER site.

The workshop consisted of a pre-workshop meeting and reading materials distributed to the participants. In Lyon, we had introductory lectures and hands-on exercises on using eLTER tools. We also visited one near by eLTER Site, Yzeron catchment.

3.1.3 Feedback

We collected feedback after each session using Menti. In addition, we sent a general feedback questionnaire to participants, and got nine answers. Most of them ranked the workshop in general (in terms of organisation, structure, content, etc.) good (6 responses), 3 excellent and one so-so. Free comments also address the general level of happiness and satisfaction:

Big thanks to the organizers, everything worked really well!

I am thoroughly impressed with the level of organization demonstrated. This level of professionalism is truly commendable. Thank you for delivering such a well-planned and executed event.

Thanks again for the organization of the workshop and to all teachers.

Figure 1: Responses of participants to post-workshop feedback questionnaire on different statements (Total 9 responses).

Looking more in detail for different sessions, participants were most happy with ReLTER (Figure 2) and DataLabs. This is also shown by additional answers to the question “What was most interesting?”:

I was only able to really follow and understand the ReLTER part and it was very nice because the presentation went slowly and the teachers made a brief introduction to the tools

ReLTER package and DataLabs in general. Those trainings were also thought true that made them more interesting and easy to follow

Python DEIMS

DEIMS + ReLTER

Figure 2: Responses of participants to post-workshop feedback questionnaire on statement “The workshop met my expectations” (Total 9 responses).

On the other hand, when asking about the irritating and annoying or difficult aspects of the workshop, the different level of previous knowledge participants had clearly influenced the experience, especially regarding the programming languages. Speed of the presentations was also mentioned.

Not being able to use python and other programming languages

Would have been good to give some basic list of python commands in advance or some small pre assignment to work a little bit with python, since the qgis exercise was only to bring a csv file to the system that added no knowledge and the other was more coding.

The session about the DataLabs went too fast. It would have been useful to have the presentation to be able to have the link and requirements (the presenter was changing the screens very quickly). The DataLabs is obviously not dimensioned for a massive usage.

For the PhenoApp session, there were several technical problems, which is visible in the responses. This underlines the importance of careful preparation of all the trainers, and testing of the system, which might be different than what the trainer is generally using, beforehand, and thinking of options if the internet or the software crashes down.

Last session with pheno-app was really irritating. People should be more prepared with their training and test what works and what doesn't. There is no point in running through something that people cannot follow. And I feel that I have wasted my time. I decided to stay until the end, but I would not have missed much by flying home already on Thursday. It was a frustrating afternoon in many ways.

Phenoapp did not work at all for me.

As I will work on phenology and with phenocams I was really interested in the PhenoApp. Unfortunately, the session was quite chaotic.

As organisers, we can be more on the point of what is available at the site, encourage preparation and testing, and ask trainers to provide materials, or small tasks for participants to be done before the actual workshop.

Participants also gave valuable feedback on the future development to the workshop by answering the question “What could be done differently”:

I think the DataLabs session would require more time to be able to follow how it works (some basics like what was done for ReLTER) and maybe be less ambitious but take time to explain more in details the things.

Well. Training is not easy, better preparations and possible pre-assignments would have helped. Some exercises with ReLTER package where you bring your own national datasets what you are interested to the system might be nice.

Maybe limit the hands on session to the more basic things, and keep some of the possible things to do as a demo. Unexpected bugs are part of the exercise but once we lost a bit of time on our own process, it became hard to follow (depending on each one computer's specifications, knowlegde, etc.).

While verbal communication is a crucial aspect of any event, I believe that incorporating an open chat platform can provide an additional layer of convenience and efficiency in sharing information and links. This can enhance the overall communication experience during the event.

3.1.4 Workshop output

In the feedback questionnaire we also asked what participants learned. In free comments participants mentioned increasing understanding of different tools. Especially, ReLTER was mentioned several times.

Some vague ideas (but better than before) of how a DataLabs is functioning

What tools exist and how they work

RELTER mostly, a bit a python. But mostly the great connection between existing tools and very useful tips and ways of working that are precious

I learned a bit more about Python and the use and potential of DEIMS and the ReLTER Package

New tools useful for my daily work, in particular the Cookie cutting tool and ReLTER

In additional comments there were some remarks on running a workshop.

Given my agenda, not sure I will use the tools soon, but as a network manager, I think that tools like DEIMS package or ReLTER could be useful to draw updated maps of our network or on the measured variables for instance

Big thanks to the presenter and those with ReLTER package. Other people should learn from them how to organize and run a workshop. Also I think you are at the wrong place, if you are not willing to modify your training according to suggestions. If people were able to follow the R package, it should not be that difficult to do the same with python.

The resources shared are very precious for long term learning!

We are centrally organising the framework in which the training is given, but each trainer is organising and running their session as they think best. In the future, we would further underline what is expected from the trainers and emphasise the importance of testing the functionality of the tools and encourage them to provide pre-workshop material that would help participants to get prepared. The on-line pre-workshop meeting was planned for this purpose.

3.2 On-Site event: eLTER Site and Platforms Forum

3.2.1 Workshop content

The meeting took place on 2-5 October 2023 in Lunz, Austria. The general programme is presented below, and the details in Annex 7.4.

Monday 2 October 2023

- Welcome and Icebreaker with site information (Coordination)
- Multi-site data usage (Coordination)

Tuesday 3 October 2023

- General eLTER update (Coordination)
- Discussions around Standard Observation, site labelling & services (UFZ, EAA, CSIC, CEH)
- Site visit of WasserCluster Lunz
- Science at Lunz and LTSER Eisenwurzen (EAA)
- Discussions - joint activities across sites

Wednesday 4 October 2023

- SPF activities and Working Groups
 - WG: (1) Data; (2) Training; (3) Funding
 - Activities: (1) LTSER platforms; (2) DEIMSLTSER platforms
- Informal discussions and interactions

Thursday 5 October 2023

- Wrap up, reflection & next steps

A total of 70 participants from 18 countries were present at the Workshop.

Figure 3: Group picture

Figure 4: Working session at Lunz

3.2.2 Feedback

A feedback questionnaire was submitted at the end of the workshop. A total of 33 participants answered the questionnaire.

Open feedback on the meeting

“great venue and great organisation”

“Communication was excellent except for the final registration, which was a bit late. It would have been great if the final confirming/cancelling of our registration would have been a bit earlier (e.g. 2 months before the meeting, maybe still without knowing the final program. However, this is probably a matter of taste; many people may like to be flexible until the latest possible point of time.”

“I hardly give the best score but here I cannot do it otherwise :-)”

“very nice to a) be at a field station and b) have some distance between hotel and venue so some leg-stretching was a natural part of the program”

“It was a perfect mixture of informal and structured programme. Very nicely balanced time for conference and time for exploring the site (Tue afternoon site visit and Wed afternoon hike) while networking with colleagues. Time for break-out groups was somehow a bit short (but probably this was good to not get lost too much into details).”

“It was really interesting to get an insight what scientific focus austrian sites have. In future it would be nice to hear more about LTER per se, what category they have and strategies are used on the site. How they deal with all ;) Some kind Nationalpark Gesäuse did..”

“4 days are maybe a bit too long”

What were the most meaningful insights that you gained from SPF05?

“Exchange knowledge with participants. Clarifying methodologies.”

“Meeting in person more site coordinators. Sharing problems and possible decisions.”

“Getting a better idea of the status of eLTER RI progress across the continent”

3.3 Online training events

3.3.1 Time series analysis for ecologists' workshops

The first on line workshop that we organised was related to data analyses. The initiative came from a member of the training working group, Ulrike Obbertegger (FEM-CRI, Italy), who was willing to share her knowledge on using R in analysing long-term ecological data. The topic appeared to be very popular. The first version of the webinar was run twice, 1st December 2021 and 24th January 2022, and all together there were 886 registrations for these workshops. The follow-up workshop was organised 21st March 2022, and for this, there were 187 registrations.

The workshop included exemplary data and R-code that were provided about a week before the online workshop.

The webinars were recorded and videos produced from them and made available through Youtube (first workshop: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-uOJ8qhMKZM&list=PLrd-B-OSwd9fG8FrFqbu58b9V-Au1YIHm&index=9>, 693 views; second workshop:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=c-0rqaUdm7Y&list=PLrd-B-OSwd9fG8FrFqbu58b9V-Au1YIHm&index=10>, 124 views).

The popularity of these workshops shows that the support on time series analysis is needed.

3.3.2 SPF webinars

The SPF webinars have been the most regular training events organised. We have aimed at having about one webinar per month. The webinars and number of registrations and participants are in Table 1.

In the SPF webinar, the proposed topics aim to cover the different interests and needs of SPCs and other persons working on eLTER Sites and eLTSER platforms. The topics of SPF webinars have ranged from presentation of research done at Sites and Platform to more concrete topics related to running a site like data management or different measuring methods and analyses. Other activities such as introduction of other projects and diversity, equity and inclusion perspectives have also been presented.

Table 1: Organised SPF webinars.

Date	Webinar title	Speakers	Number of registrations	Number of participants	Link to the recording in Youtube
2022-10-12	LIFEPLAN ERC Synergy project	Bess Harwick (UH), Otso Ovaskainen (JyU)	97		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HMtW5rQK17k&list=PLrd-B-OSwd9epgkbT_zQatMyEu-UbeyKI&index=5
2022-11-23	Transnational and Remote Access (TA&RA) to eLTER sites	Ulf Mallast (UFZ), Maria Jose Fernandez Alonso, Jan Pisek	72		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dGBa9oNbtqQ&list=PLrd-B-OSwd9epgkbT_zQatMyEu-UbeyKI&index=6
2023-02-01	iNaturalist	Inês Rosário (FC.ID), Patricia	116		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=U5eAuK9nSf8
2023-03-08	SITES Spectral - Remote sensing	Lars Eklundh, Shangharsha Thapa	139		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cqVLfyt1as4&t=86s
2023-04-05	Early career science	Christian Poppe (FZJ), Alexandre Lhosmot	55		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mkdgiV6HQj8&t=48s https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8b_Vh0qL8IE
2023-09-12	FAIR principles - I & R	Hanna Koivula (CSC); Pasi Kolari (UH)	93	50	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2VqH4-yK2iM
2023-11-08	4th TA&RA CALL	Ulf Mallast (UFZ), Tudor Racoviceanu (UNIBUC), Alexandra Hillebrand-Voiculescu, Kevin Mganga	31	27	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-QTsqCkwS04

2023-11-22	Data publications	Tanja Lindholm (UH); Allan T Souza (UH)	123	61	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2W9gWBirqYk
2024-01-24	Aquatic Remote Sensing	Igor Ogashawara	70	41	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xmLQGNGcrBM&t=1s
2024-02-14	LTSER Platforms	Veronika Gaube (EAA), Daniel Orenstein (IIT)	117	70	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T7vpRbK7RQs&t=4s
2024-03-06	DEI	Rebecca Barnes	40	26	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JwSAzUea90I
2024-04-04	Standard Observation cost estimate app	Allan Souza (UH), Steffen Zacharias (UFZ), Jaana Bäck (UH), Syed Ashrafal Alam (UH)	101	64	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=umLumdmWQQ&t=2568s

The topics for future SPF webinars are for example WAILS approach from different perspectives, mobilising the legacy data and Market Place.

4 Finding and Accessing Training Events

4.1 Advertisement

eLTER training has been mainly advertised through project email lists, eLTER webpage and Social media posts. In addition to the SPC list, which consists of SPCs listed as contact for Site/Platform in DEIMS, we have been building an SPF email lists, where people registering to eLTER SPF events can subscribe and which is used in advertising SPF events, such as webinars and trainings. In addition, the workshops have been advertised for all eLTER PLUS and eLTER PPP participants. On eLTER webpage, each SPF webinar has an event page with a short description of the content, agenda and link to registration. Upcoming training events and webinars have been also verbally advertised in various (on-line) project meetings, and listed as upcoming events on eLTER Newsletter. In addition, some of the National Networks distributed the advertisement at national scale.

The feedback collected after the Time-series analysis workshops shows that most of the participants have heard about the event either through a colleague (60 responses) or through email (54 responses). Social media posts played a smaller role (12 responses), as well as eLTER website (7 responses).

4.2 Accessibility

In order to increase the accessibility of eLTER training, the on-line events have been open to all, independently if persons are involved in the ongoing eLTER projects. However, registration has been required to allow us to follow the expected participation. This has also been a security measure, as the link to join the event has been sent only to registered persons.

The on-site training event (eLTER tools, see Chapter 3.1) was also openly available for all. eLTER PLUS project covered the lunch, and there was no participation fee, but participants needed to organise and pay for their travels and accommodation.

To make the information available also to those who cannot participate in the webinars, we have recorded them. The recordings were further edited to produce training videos which are available through eLTER YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@elter5490/featured>).

In addition, we have built a training section on eLTER website (<https://elter-ri.eu/elter-training>). The training has been categorised under specific topics to facilitate findability of the materials (Figure 3). The training page, in addition to videos, also collects other relevant materials, like relevant deliverables, documents and info sheets.

Figure 3: Screenshot of eLTER Training website (<https://elter-ri.eu/elter-training>) showing the organisation of materials following different topics.

4.3 Training impact

In general, the feedback on organised training events has been positive. In addition to increasing participants' knowledge on the topic itself, training also contributes to the general visibility and awareness of eLTER and allows for potential future collaborations. About half of the participants of the Time-series analyses workshop had not heard about eLTER before the webinar, which clearly indicates the general value of the training.

5 Future training needs

Data continues being one of the topical issues for Sites and Platforms. Data availability is also crucial for the functioning of eLTER RI and its ability to provide services. It is encouraging to see that this comes up also in SPCs' questionnaire, where "Data sharing through the eLTER services (e.g., data sharing including harmonisation and storage & preparing metadata; FAIR principle)" was the most selected answer for topics where training is needed. It also shows that the support for this has been under development. When the work proceeds and develop during the project and in eLTER RI, it is important that the results are clearly communicated to SPCs.

"Publishing datasets and data papers (e.g., GBIF, biodiversity data)" also received many votes. This is good to see as this will also support the data availability and correct referring to the data supporting the recognition of the work done at Sites and Platforms. Although there is probably work to be done in attitude change making people aware of the importance of data publishing, the result shows that many already recognise the need but might not be familiar with the different ways of publishing data. We have already organised one webinar around this topic, and the video is available in YouTube, but it is worth giving the topic some visibility and maybe also organising a hands-on session on this.

“Interaction with stakeholders” raised up as the most wanted training topic regarding Science Communication, while “Funding opportunities” was the most mentioned in the Site Management category. Naturally long-term funding forms the bases for the functioning and development of a Site/Platform and for the whole eLTER RI, and therefore any support we can offer is valuable. This has been done partly through National Coordinators providing materials to be used in the interaction with Stakeholders, but the process would benefit from better organisation and regular updating of the materials. In addition, specific sessions to inform not only NCs but also SPCs could be organised.

Once the work on eLTER Standard Observations and protocols is finished (WP3), different trainings related to them are needed, such as monitoring procedures.

6 Acknowledgements

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7 Annexes

7.1 Annex 1: SPCs' training needs questionnaire 1

7.1.1 Form to fill

This questionnaire is prepared by the SPF training working group. This is your opportunity to express your thoughts and influence activities. The results will be the basis for further developments and action plans.

Please fill it latest 12th July 2021.

SPCs' training needs

Intro

What type of ecosystem are you involved in? *

- marine
- costal
- rivers
- lakes
- terrestrial
- other

If other, please specify:

What type of training do you like to have?

Tick the boxes for the trainings you are interested and consider useful.

Data management: (this aspect may be developed with the group on data management)

- Data sharing through the eLTER services
- Data sharing including harmonisation and storage
- Describing metadata in DEIMS-SDR
- Responding to eLTER data calls
- Publishing datasets and data papers
- Digital Asset Register
- Data access/visualising data (Data Integration Platform/Ecosense)
- Workflows for quality control
- Preparing metadata
- Other:

If other, please specify:

Access

- Support to site platform coordinators on providing access to sites (Transnational Access and Remote Access)
- Support to SPCs on providing access to data (Virtual Access)

Science communication and involvement of citizens

- eLTER Data labs as the environment to do analyses (i.e. working collaboratively on analytics)
- GIS tools (with tools)
- Bayesian analysis
- Machine Learning
- Time-series analysis
- Spatial analysis
- Calculation of socio-ecological indicators
- Remote sensing and earth observation (EO) data
- Other

If other, please specify:

New technologies

- Sensor based
- High Throughput Sequencing analyses
- Other:

If other, please specify:

Monitoring procedures

- Introduction to the eLTER Service Portfolio concept
- Establish collaborations with other LTER sites to organize training courses to scientific public, stakeholders
- eLTER Standard Observations - abiotic site characteristics
- eLTER Standard Observations - socio-ecology
- eLTER Standard Observations - biotic heterogeneity
- eLTER Standard Observations - energy budget
- eLTER Standard Observations - water budget
- eLTER Standard Observations - matter budget
- Site management
- Cost analysis and budgeting at eLTER sites (cost book)
- Funding programmes
- Colocation with other Research Infrastructures
- National ESFRI processes
- Other

If other, please specify:

Other

What do you expect from the SPF training group (please write your ideas about this)?

Proceed

7.1.2 Results

Altogether, we received 89 responses to the first SPC training needs questionnaire. The results are presented below.

What type of ecosystem are you involved in?

Figure 5: What type of ecosystem are you involved in?

Table A1: Number of responses on question “What type of training do you like to have?”. Total number of replies to the questionnaire was 89. It was possible to select several topics in each section.

Training topic	nbr of responses
Data management	
Publishing datasets and data papers	52
Data sharing through the eLTER services	49
Data sharing including harmonisation and storage	49
Data access/visualising data (Data Integration Platform/Ecosense)	40
Describing metadata in DEIMS-SDR	37
Responding to eLTER data calls	37
Workflows for quality control	32
Preparing metadata	29
Digital Asset Register	14
Access	
Support to site platform coordinators on providing access to sites (Transnational Access and Remote Access)	41
Support to SPCs on providing access to data (Virtual Access)	28
Data analyses*	
Time-series analysis	55
Spatial analysis	40
Remote sensing and earth observation (EO) data	36

eLTER Data labs as the environment to do analyses (i.e. working collaboratively on analytics)	33
Calculation of socio-ecological indicators	33
GIS tools (with tools)	31
Bayesian analysis	27
Machine Learning	21
New technologies	
Sensor based	59
High Throughput Sequencing analyses	19
Monitoring procedures	
eLTER Standard Observations - abiotic site characteristics	44
eLTER Standard Observations - biotic heterogeneity	42
eLTER Standard Observations - water budget	37
Site management	33
Establish collaborations with other LTER sites to organize training courses to scientific public, stakeholders	32
eLTER Standard Observations - socio-ecology	32
Funding programmes	31
eLTER Standard Observations - matter budget	29
eLTER Standard Observations - energy budget	28
Cost analysis and budgeting at eLTER sites (cost book)	27
Introduction to the eLTER Service Portfolio concept	26
Colocation with other Research Infrastructures	20
National ESFRI processes	20

*This section was accidentally named as “Science communication and involvement of citizens” in the questionnaire.

In addition, there was always the option to select “other” and to give suggestions.

Data management:

If other,

- datasets publishing and sharing and harmonization
- data services beyond eLTER - what is out there for ecologists
- GIS & RS
- Assignment of DOI to databases

At the end of the survey, the respondents gave open answers about their expectations and ideas for SPF training working group.

What do you expect from the SPF training group (please write your ideas about this)?

- *Assistance with the day to day business of being an eLTER platform.*
- *Basic knowledge in requirements for data collection, loading, storage, exchange. Calibration of methods in data collection. Coordination between sites, establishing communication and management exchange.*
- *collaboration, visiting laboratories, field work*
- *exchange of ideas / plans with other SC for coordinated development of data sharing etc.*
- *Experience sharing among sites and platform managers, peer learning*
- *gain common environment and professionalism for feasible and active engagement in LTER-RI. Increase cooperation/sharing our experience and methods/techniques.*

-
- *I expect workshops and seminars to share skills as well as a toolbox gathering key references and tools on the subject*
 - *I favour training events which are provided as virtual events that are recorded so I can watch again or watch if I miss them. I am not bothered about the 'professional' style of the event but welcome informality. Lectures with written questions in a chat facility that everyone can see is good. This enables others to answer (not only the presenter) and encourages chat during the lecture and fosters a full and open exchange of knowledge.*
 - *I have only very vague expectations. It would be useful to first get acquainted with the basics of the SPF functioning.*
 - *interaction increase between sites*
 - *Lessons learned to optimise efforts*
 - *Mostly, I'd like these training groups to inspire other network scientists to be more enthusiastic and engaged in collaborative eLTER work.*
 - *Organizing expert presentations with printed materials*
 - *Primarily education and coordination of method and data harmonisation. Also, methods in data analysis and evaluation.*
 - *Submission of materials on the training topic.*
 - *to create a uniform way for collecting data, maybe working with the same collecting apps or demand for certain consistent data to be in (for example, date, location, latine species name etc.)*
 - *To have training to improve our platforms and sites data management and to have a better integration with the eLTER network*
 - *training for different career stages*

7.2 Annex 2: SPCs' training needs questionnaire 2

7.2.1 Form to fill

This questionnaire is prepared by the SPF training working group. This is your opportunity to express your thoughts and influence activities. The results will be the basis for further developments and action plans.

Please fill it latest 1st of September 2023.

SPCs' training needs v02

Intro

What type of ecosystem are you involved in? *

- marine and/or coastal
- rivers
- lakes and/or reservoirs
- terrestrial
- other
- transitional

If other, please specify:

What type of training do you like to have?

Tick the boxes for the trainings you are interested in and consider useful.

Data management: (this aspect may be developed with the group on data management)

- Data sharing through the eLTER services (e.g., data sharing including harmonisation and storage & preparing metadata; FAIR principle)
- Using DEIMS-SDR for describing sites and datasets
- Publishing datasets and data papers (e.g., GBIF, biodiversity data)
- Digital Asset Register
- Other:

If other, please specify:

Access

- Support to Site & Platform Coordinators on providing access to sites (Transnational Access and Remote Access)
- Support to SPCs on providing access to data (Virtual Access)

Science communication

- Interaction with stakeholders
- Effectiveness in policy formulation
- Citizen science
- Presentation skills
- Other:

If other, please specify:

Data usage & analysis

- DataLabs as the environment to do analyses (i.e. working collaboratively on analytics)
- ReLTER (R-package)
- Data access/visualising data (Data Integration Platform)
- GIS
- Bayesian analysis
- Machine learning
- Time-series analysis
- Spatial analysis
- Calculation of socio-ecological & ecosystem services indicators
- Climate-Water-Food Nexus (CWF): tools applied in nexus situation
- Remote sensing and earth observation (EO) data
- Other

If other, please specify:

New technologies

- Sensor based (e.g. High-frequency sensors; ZooScan)
- High Throughput Sequencing analysis (eDNA)
- Other

If other, please specify:

Site management

- Networking
- Cost book
- Funding opportunities
- Colocation with other Research Infrastructures (e.g. ICOS, LifeWatch)
- Site labelling process (tools to evaluate the "status" of a site in terms of category)
- Other:

If other, please specify:

Format of a training:

- In-person
- On line
- Hybrid

Duration

- Short workshop (~ 1hr)
- Medium workshop (~ 2-3 hrs)
- Long workshop (~ 1-2 days)

Other wishes/training needs

Volunteering

volunteer for a specific topic
(put email address + topic
that you would like to give a
training on)

Proceed

Save

7.2.2 Results

Figure 6: Ecosystems that the respondents are involved in. Total number of responses 134 (90 respondents).

Table A2: Number of responses on question “What type of training do you like to have?”. Total number of replies to the questionnaire was 90. It was possible to select several topics in each section.

Training topic	nbr of responses
Data management	
Data sharing through the eLTER services (e.g., data sharing including harmonisation and storage & preparing metadata; FAIR principle)	61
Publishing datasets and data papers (e.g., GBIF, biodiversity data)	49
Using DEIMS-SDR for describing sites and datasets	36
Digital Asset Register	9
Access	
Support to Site & Platform Coordinators on providing access to sites (Transnational Access and Remote Access)	41
Support to SPCs on providing access to data (Virtual Access)	38
Science communication	
Interaction with stakeholders	49
Citizen science	33
Effectiveness in policy formulation	24
Presentation skills	13
Data usage & analysis	
Time-series analysis	45
DataLabs as the environment to do analyses (i.e. working collaboratively on analytics)	37
Data access/visualising data (Data Integration Platform)	35
Calculation of socio-ecological & ecosystem services indicators	35
ReLTER (R-package)	29
Spatial analysis	29
GIS	28
Remote sensing and earth observation (EO) data	27
Machine learning	20

Bayesian analysis	19
Climate-Water-Food Nexus (CWF): tools applied in nexus situation	10
New technologies	
Sensor based (e.g. High-frequency sensors; ZooScan)	41
High Throughput Sequencing analysis (eDNA)	25
Site management	
Funding opportunities	43
Site labelling process (tools to evaluate the "status" of a site in terms of category)	34
Colocation with other Research Infrastructures (e.g. ICOS, LifeWatch)	33
Networking	25
Cost book	20

In addition, there was always the option to select “other” and to give suggestion. Received answers are listed below.

Data management

- *tools for data control and validation*
- *More WALLS and social-ecology to encourage eLTER-wide collaborations.*

Science communication:

- *Using fuzzy cognitive mapping and other participatory research tools.*

New technologies

- *Telemetry (transmitting real time data from data loggers)*
- *microplastic analysis*
- *IoT, communication, transfer of data*
- *instrumentation for the standard observation, overview, photos, list of companies*
- *hands-on workshop for use/operation of specific sensors*

Last section in the questionnaire asked about the preferences regarding the practical organization of training.

Figure 7: Format of training (total number of responses 136).

Figure 8: Duration of training (total number of responses 129).

7.3 Annex 3: eLTER software tools workshop

7.3.1 Agenda

eLTER tools workshop

7-9 February 2023

INRAE, Lyon, France

Tuesday 7 February

9-9:30 Opening

9:30-13 DataLabs (UK CEH)

- DataLabs project space
 - Using and administering your project space
 - Creating project storage (NFS and object store), uploading files
- Creating a Jupyter lab (the interface, terminal interface, kernels) and working collaboratively with it
- Creating new Conda environments and managing packages within Conda
 - Example analysis
- Create Rstudio project
 - installing packages
 - example analysis
 - manages packages within R (Packrat)
- DASK
 - Creating DASK cluster
 - Start DASK cluster, access the DASK dashboard, Perform DASK calculation, Delete DASK cluster
- SPARK
 - Creating a SPARK cluster

- Start SPARK session, perform SPARK calculation
- Delete SPARK Cluster
- Using object storage in DataLabs
 - python
 - terminal
- Jupyter Dashboards, using Panel and Voila (Creating and using Panel and Voila sites)
- Using RShiny (Setting up Rshiny sites)
- Using the DataLabs catalogue
- User administration tools

13-14 Lunch

14-17 DEIMS (EAA)

- General overview (scope, usage, quality assurance, basic search functionality)
- GeoData Services (GIS knowledge recommended)
- REST-API (basic web programming knowledge recommended)
- deimsPy (basic Python knowledge is recommended)
 - Showing examples using datalabs
- Exercise: Working with deims data (probably 2-3 different options depending on skills and interests)
 - Desktop GIS exercise (e.g. making maps of sites and networks using deims data) OR
 - Query deims using either
 - deimsPy OR
 - REST-API

Wednesday 8 February

9-13 Cookie cutting (UK CEH)

- Existing data overview
- Compatible data types
- Processing data

13-14 lunch**14-17 Site visit, Yzeron catchment ([in DEIMS](#) and [here](#))****Thursday 9 February****9-13 ReLTER (BGU; CNR; CNR)**

- Description about the package's approach
- Examples of different functions, including a description of the outputs of the functions
- Advanced functions: interaction with remote sensing products, biodiversity repositories, data shared with DEIMS-SDR, Zenodo upload and download dataset, interaction with SOS service for download data
- A mentimeter session will be proposed to collect suggestions for new functions or improvements to the package.

13-14 Lunch**14-16:30 Pheno-App (CSIC)**

- Access to GeeLTERMap (through either Datalab or Google colab)
- demonstration of the different available products (MODIS, S2 Phenopy NDVI, Copernicus VPP PPI)
- Available metrics (SOS, EOS, LOS)
- Data download for specific eLTER site
- In situ data upload for eLTER sites with available historical datasets

16:30-17 Closing up**7.3.2 Session feedback**

Summary of the Menti Feedback Session for All Workshop Sessions. The question posed was: *“What did you enjoy during the session?”*

7.3.2.1 DataLabs

Figure 9: Feedback session DATALABS: What did you enjoy during session?

18 respondents

What did you enjoy during session?

- finally learned how jupyterlabs works
- very interesting approach to cloud analysis for LTER data
- that I was not the only one having problems to follow sometimes ;)
- I like that it was really focused on put the hands on the code and the tools themselves
- hands on session
- good intro to Datalabs
- nicely, interactively presented
- I am still lost
- The general explanation about the use of Datalabs and its possibility to share analysis at community level
- Presenter was well prepared for the session, esppecially taking into account large number of participants
- I've heart a lot of new things that I may introduce in my work
- it was good and useful
- need to manage to work with it (not done at all right now) to decide
- pandas basics use
- Possibilities to cooperative workspace

What additional properties would you like to see in DataLabs?

- interoperability
- Who can do what? who can use it? Information about accessibility and target group(s)
- a list of sites and their functions and how to use them (as soon as there are more of them created)
- Basics of using Jupyter, R.
- Cross analyses among sites
- chat function within a project would be nice
- Maybe it already exists there, but it wasn't mentioned: version control (git).
- clear licenses for the data
- I would like to know how in general use it in my particular work. How to imply it.
- may have ideas when I really manage to work with it (not done at all yet)

- more detailed help

7.3.2.2 DEIMS

Figure 10: Feedback session DEIMS: What did you enjoy during session?

15 respondents

What did you enjoy during session?

- Friendliness
- Interesting to use the deims python package.
- I am worried about Christoph. He is really addicted to coffee.
- seeing Christoph suffering ;)
- it was easy to understand before must use it
- To see other people struggling with boundaries as well
- good presentation and ideas of practical work

What additional information/knowledge/understanding about DEIMS you would need?

- A tutorial with deims python notebooks as examples.
- I am worried that some questions in the DEIMS sheet are answered by pure guess
- More step by step tutorials and videos
- a tutorial how to use deims.py
- For the beginning I would need to learn some programming. This is not up to you. ;)
- Knowing python a bit more would help a lot. Really simple tutorials, please!
- how to use the available information
- better explanation
- A quick tutorial on how to use the DEIMS information on GIS
- I know GIS very well, but this was not successful even with some help
- some statistics who uses deims, how often DOIs are cited

7.3.2.3 Cookie cutting

Figure 11: Feedback session Cookie cutting: What did you enjoy during session?

18 respondents

What did you enjoy during session?

- Application of Git
- very interesting applications for our LTER sites
- The shiny app looks interesting!
- Application of Jupyter.
- nice application of jupiter
- I was missing the fundamentals of GIT
- my first steps in R and the well designed tutorial
- it was very clear explained
- I am still wondering about the security of this type of apps
- `alert('does XSS work?');`
- the tool is easily applicable to a number of necessity for researches at LTER site
- The intention to run the tool with so many users
- tutorial

What additional information would you need in order to use Cookie-cutting in your work?

- some kind of a step by step tutorial
- tutorial
- None

7.3.2.4 ReLTER

The ReLTER session trainers organised their own feedback to which I unfortunately do not have access.

7.3.2.5 Pheno-App

Figure 12: Feedback session Pheno-App: What did you enjoy during session?

16 respondents

What did you enjoy during session?

- very future tools
- interactive python maps
- For me it was interesting to see the Google Earth Engine integration in Python.
- Expectations on this tool increased
- Interesting things. Maybe next time more time to get a better idea.
- working with satellite data
- It sees a very useful tool
- It was step by step and I can followed it
- Powerful new tools
- might be a very useful and versatile tool

What additional information/knowledge/understanding about Pheno-App you would need?

- maybe some satellite data basics (at least the bands that are implemented)
- Hard to say
- How to combine the satellite data with other sources, like phenocam and ground observation data

7.4Annex 4: eLTER Sites and Platforms Forum - Lunz

7.4.1 Agenda

eLTER Sites and Platforms Forum

2nd –5th of October 2023

Wassercluster, Lunz am See, Austria

Monday 2nd Oct

14:30 Hired bus from St. Pölten station to Lunz

Network and collaborate among SPCs

16:30 Registration & coffee at Wassercluster Lunz

17:00 Welcome to SPF05

- Meeting overview
- Ice breaker ● Sites and Platforms as eLTER backbones

19:00 Social evening with local snacks & drinks at Wassercluster Lunz

Tuesday 3rd Oct

Guide the future eLTER RI process

9:00 General eLTER update 1

- WAILS concept at eLTER
- Standard Observations and Network design

10:30 Coffee break

11:00 General eLTER update 2

- Current network design towards the formal Site labelling
- Governance

12:00 Lunch at Seeterasse

13:00 Overview of Eisenwurzen sites

- Eisenwurzen platform and its sites

14:30 WCL Site Visit (Outdoors)

- Tour of the WCL site

16:00 Coffee break

16:30 Interdisciplinary research

- Breakout #1: eLTSE Platforms & Socio-ecological component
- Breakout #2: Interdisciplinary science

17:30 End of the day

19:00 Dinner (at own cost)

Wednesday 4th Oct***Synergies across SPF*****9:00 eLTER Data**

- Services for Sites and Platforms: data calls
- Services for Sites and Platforms: data mobilisation

10:30 Coffee Break

11:00 SPF Working Groups & Activities

- Breakout #1: Data Management & Information Clusters
- Breakout #2: Training
- Breakout #3: Funding

12:00 Lunch at Seeterasse

13:00 Excursion & Interactions (Outdoors)

- Option 1: Hike to Obersee (4-5 hours)
- Option 2: Walk around the lake Lunz & stop at the visitor centre

19:00 Group dinner at Landhotel Zellerhof (paid by eLTER)

Thursday 6th Oct**9:00 Wrap-up & next steps**

- Collecting and prioritization of meeting outcomes
- SPF activities and upcoming events
- Site information exchange

- Wrap-up & thank you

11:00 End of the programme

11:30 Bus from Lunz (Landhotel Zellerhof) to St Pölten railway station